

2015

***Aarhat Multidisciplinary
International Education
Research Journal (AMIERJ)***

***(Bi-Monthly)
Peer-Reviewed Journal
Impact factor: 0.948***

VOL - IV Issues: I

***Chief-Editor:
Ubale Amol Baban***

30/11/2014

STUDY OF CYBER CRIME AWARENESS AMONG PERSPECTIVE TEACHERS

Dr. Balbirsingh,

Associate Professor,

Tika Ram College of Education, Sonipat,

Haryana

Ishu Jaglan,

Research Scholar

Abstract

In the present day world, India has witnessed an unprecedented index of Cyber crimes whether they pertain to Trojan attacks, salami attacks, e-mail bombing, DOS attacks, information theft, or the most common offence of hacking. The present study examines the cyber crime awareness among M.Ed. students.. The research was conducted on 80 M. Ed. students equally from rural and urban areas, randomly selected from six college of education of Sonipat and Rohtak districts in Haryana. Out of which 40 students are with U. G. degree and 40 students are with P. G. degree. “-Cyber Crime Awareness Scale” developed by “ Dr. Rajasekar” was used to collect the data regarding the cyber crime awareness among M.Ed. students.. The results of the study indicated that significant difference was not observed between M. Ed. Students regarding their place of study, level of education and also no significant difference was found between M. Ed. Students having own computer and not having own computer regarding the cyber crime awareness.

Introduction

In the present day world, India has witnessed a huge increase in Cyber crimes whether they pertain to Trojan attacks, salami attacks, e-mail bombing, DOS attacks, information theft, or the most common offence of hacking the data or system to commit crime. The first recorded cyber crime took place in the year 1820 which is not surprising considering the fact that the

Aarhat Multidisciplinary International Education Research Journal (AMIERJ)

(Bi-Monthly)

Peer-Reviewed Journal

Vol No IV Issues I

Jan 2015

ISSN 2278-5655

abacus, which is thought to be the earliest form of a computer, has been around since 3500 B.C. in India, Japan and China. The era of modern computers, however, began with the analytical engine of Charles Babbage. In 1820, Joseph-Marie Jacquard, a textile manufacturer in France, produced the loom. This device allowed the repetition of a series of steps in the weaving of special fabrics. This resulted in a fear amongst Jacquard's employees that their traditional employment and livelihood were being threatened. They committed acts of sabotage to discourage Jacquard from further use of the new technology. This was the first recorded cyber crime. Despite technological measures being adopted by corporate organizations and individuals, we have witnessed that the frequency of cyber crimes has increased over the last decade. Cyber crime refers to the act of performing a criminal act using computer or cyberspace (the Internet network), as the communication vehicle. Though there is no technical definition by any statutory body for Cyber crime, it is broadly defined by the Computer Crime Research Center as - "Crimes committed on the internet using the computer either as a tool or a targeted victim." All types of cyber crimes involve both the computer and the person behind it as victims; it just depends on which of the two is the main target. Cyber crime could include anything as simple as downloading illegal music files to stealing millions of dollars from online bank accounts. Cyber crime could also include non-monetary offenses, such as creating and distributing small or large programs written by programmers called viruses on other computers or posting confidential business information on the Internet. An important form of cyber crime is identity theft, in which criminals use the Internet to steal personal information from other users. Various types of social networking sites are used for this purpose to find the identity of interested peoples. There are two ways this is done - phishing and harming, both methods lure users to fake websites, where they are asked to enter personal information. This includes login information, such as usernames and passwords, phone numbers, addresses, credit card numbers, bank account numbers, and other information criminals can use to "steal" another person's identity. According to Taylor(1999), when speaking about cybercrime, usually it is about two major categories of offences. In one, a computer connected to a network is the target of the offence and this is the case of attacks on network confidentiality, integrity and availability. The other category consists of traditional offences such as theft, fraud, and forgery which are committed with the assistance or by means

of computers connected to a network, computer networks and related information and communications and technology.

Objective of the study:-

1. To compare the cyber crime awareness among M.Ed. students residing in rural and urban areas.
2. To compare the cyber crime awareness among U.G. and P.G. M.Ed. students.
3. To compare the cyber crime awareness among M.Ed. students having own computers and not having own computers.

Hypotheses of the study:-

1. There is no significant difference among M.Ed. students residing in rural and urban areas regarding the cyber crime awareness.
2. There is no significant difference among U.G. and P.G. M.Ed. students regarding the cyber crime awareness.
3. There is no significant difference among M.Ed. students having own computers and not having own computers regarding the cyber crime awareness.

Methodology

Sample of the study

Sample of the present study consisted of 80 M. Ed. students equally from rural and urban areas, randomly selected from six college of education of Sonipat and Rohtak districts in Haryana. Out of which 40 students are with U. G. degree and 40 students are with P. G. degree.

Tools Used

In the present study “Cyber Crime Awareness Scale” developed by Dr. Rajasekar was used to collection the data regarding the cyber crime awareness among M. Ed. students.

Procedure

Descriptive survey method of research was employed for the present study. The tool employed in the study were administered on M. Ed. Students..

Analysis And Interpretation

Table 1: Mean, Standard Deviation, S.ED and 't' values of cyber crime awareness among M.Ed. Students.

M. Ed. Students	N	Mean	S.D	S.Ed	t-value	Level of significant at 0.05 level
Urban	40	135.425	18.833	3.891	0.318	Not significant
Rural	40	138.875	15.905			

The calculated t-value 0.318 in table 1 is less than the table t-value at the 0.05 significance level so the null hypothesis is accepted and we can say that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of urban and rural M.Ed. students regarding cyber crime awareness.

Table 2: Mean, Standard Deviation, S .ED and 't' values Cyber Crime Awareness Among M.Ed. Students.

M. Ed. Students	N	Mean	S.D	S.Ed	t-value	Level of significant at 0.05 level
U.G.	40	135.675	18.64292	4.108	0.5039	Not significant
P.G.	40	138.625	18.09758			

The calculated t-value 0.503955 in table 2 is less than the table t-value at the 0.05 significance level so the null hypothesis is accepted and we can say that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of U. G. and P. G. M.Ed. students regarding the cyber crime awareness.

Table 3: Mean, Standard Deviation, S.E.D and 't' values Cyber Crime Awareness Among M.Ed. Students.

M. Ed. Students	N	Mean	S.D	S.ED	t-value	Level of significant at 0.05 level
Having own computer	44	138.5682	19.1935	4.0243	0.755	Not significant
Not Having own computer	36	135.5278	16.7817			

The calculated t-value 0.755 in table 3 is less than the table t-value at the 0.05 significance level so the null hypothesis is accepted and we can say that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of M. Ed. Students, having own computer and not having own computer regarding the cyber crime awareness.

Findings

On the basis of the discussion of results and findings of the study, it is concluded that- There is insignificant difference between the M. Ed. Students studying in rural and urban areas regarding cyber crime awareness. However rural students are better on cyber crime awareness

than urban students but the difference is not significant. M. Ed. Students having postgraduate degree have better awareness for cyber crime than those students who have undergraduate degree. This means that high level of education influences awareness. In this case, the difference between two groups on cyber crime awareness is also not significant because the calculated t-value is 0.718 which is less than the table t-value at the 0.05 level of significance. As far as those M. Ed. Students are concerned that have own computer and those who do not have own computer, insignificant difference is found on cyber crime awareness as calculated t-value is 0.755. The present investigation revealed that M.Ed. students studying in the college of Education in Rohtak and Sonapat district of Haryana are having low level of awareness on cyber crime. This condition should not help them to be successful teachers. So it is suggested that M.Ed. students need to gain better information and awareness regarding cyber crime. They should balance the cyber technology and maintain the order of online law to generate the cyber age students. Institutions should work on moving to launch awareness of cyber crime programmer for M.Ed. students.

References

- Atili, A. (2011). *Wanted! Law for tackling cyber crime* (p. 41). The Nation e-Business, Messeti-Nsukka Inc.
- Baker, Glenn D. "Trespassers Will Be Prosecuted: Computer Crime In The 1990s." *Computer Law Journal* 12 (1993): 61–100.
- Charney, Scott, And Alexander, Kent. "Computer Crime." *Emory Law Journal* 45 (1996): 931–957.
- David, S, Wall. (2008). Cyber crime, media and insecurity: The shaping of public perceptions of cyber crime. *Computer & Technology*, 22 (1-2).

Copyrights Dr. Balbirsingh & Ishu Jaglan..This is an open access peer reviewed article distributed under the creative common attribution license which permits unrestricted use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provide the original work is cited.